

THE ESSENCE OF THE CONCEPT OF DEVELOPING ORGANIZATIONAL AND PROMOTIONAL QUALITIES IN PRIMARY EDUCATION TEACHERS

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Abstract: The content of this article is aimed at revealing the essence of the development of organizational and advocacy qualities in primary education teachers. Scientifically based opinions are also presented about the need to develop the characteristics of personal creativity in primary education teachers.

Key words: primary education, teacher, organization, qualities of promotion, characteristics of personal creativity, scientific considerations.

Introduction.

The development of education in the conditions of social changes and modernization of the educational system while preserving and glorifying values that have been preserved for centuries requires the training of teachers who are able to organize activities. This requirement, reflected in the state educational standards, is compatible with the issue of "organization of scheduled and extracurricular activities of primary school students", one of the objects of professional activity of graduates.

In recent years, in our republic, on the basis of national values, the heritage of enlightened figures, the normative foundations for improving education, educating the young generation in the spirit of patriotism, forming feelings of national pride, and developing professional and social training of future specialists have been created. "Using the ideas of modern enlighteners in the education of the young generation" and carrying out innovative researches are defined as leading directions. This will expand the pedagogical possibilities of teaching the

pedagogical heritage of representatives of the Jadidist movement to students of higher educational institutions.

The main part. The requirements for the educational process of higher education organizations should be aimed at creating conditions for the formation of the necessary skills and competencies of students. Because, when a teacher enters the educational process based on deep and thorough scientific knowledge in his specialty, he should have a perfect knowledge of pedagogical and psychological knowledge, creative approach to the process, and conduct his activities in the form of research. Research conducted in higher education organizations is considered scientific research, and the definitions given to scientific research should be clarified. “Scientific research is the process of discovering new knowledge and theories.”¹

“Any scientific research is a specially organized process of knowing, in which theoretical knowledge about reality is studied, assimilated and systematized”².

Guiding children's visual activity requires the educator to know what creativity is in general and children's creativity in particular, to know the specific features of children's creativity, to support the child's initiative and independence, and to work with sensitivity and courtesy. Development of necessary skills and abilities and creative potential.

The famous researcher A. Lilov expressed his understanding of creativity as follows:³ he ... has general, qualitatively new features that define it, some of which are sufficiently revealed by the theory. These natural moments of creativity are as follows: - creativity is a social phenomenon; - its deep social essence lies in the fact that it creates socially necessary and socially useful values, satisfies social needs, and especially in the fact that they are the highest concentration of the

¹ Pedagogik atamalar lug‘ati. – T.: “Qori Niyoziy” nomi-dagi O‘zPFITI, 2017. –B.26

² Педагогическое исследование: содержание и представление результатов / Е.В. Яковлев, Н.О. Яковлева. – Челябинск.: Изд-во РБИУ, 2010. – С.5.

³ Лилов А. Природа художественного творчества. [Текст] / А. Лилов. -М., 1981 г. – 91 с

changing role of a conscious social subject (class, people, society) (interacting with objective reality).

Scientists who have studied the creativity of elementary school students define creativity as follows. The famous Soviet teacher V.N. Shatskaya, talking about children's art and its importance in the formation of a child's personality, noted the following: “We consider it (children's artistic creativity) from the point of view of general aesthetic education: on the contrary, the creation of social and artistic values as the most perfect method of mastering instead dedicated to a certain art form and to the formation of an aesthetically developed personality.”

E.A.Fleurina, a well-known researcher of children's art, wrote: “We define children's art as the child's conscious drawing, modeling, construction of the surrounding reality, based on the work of imagination, its reflection, observations, as well as through words, pictures and other types of art. impressions received. The child does not passively move the environment, but processes it in connection with the accumulated experience, described attitude.”

A.A. Volkova describes the visual art of preschool children and describes it as follows: “Education of creativity has a multifaceted and complex effect on a child. Some knowledge to enrich a child's mind with different ideas means giving plenty of food for children's creativity. To teach them to look carefully, to be observant means to make their ideas clear, more complete. It helps children to repeat what they see more clearly in their work.”

Research methodology: comparative study of scientific-methodical literature, systematic analysis, pedagogical diagnosis, interview, scientific forecasting, modeling, monitoring, pedagogical experiment-testing, theoretical, empirical and practical methods are used in the article.

Analysis and results.

O.A.Abdullina developed the content and types of pedagogical skills in accordance with the development of a functional approach in her work, specific

types of work of a teacher-educator. He distinguished the following pedagogical functions:

organization of the educational process and management of learning activities of learners;

conducting educational work with students outside the classroom and managing their self-education;

“carrying out political and educational activities among the population and promoting pedagogical knowledge”;

study and transfer of advanced pedagogical experience, analysis and generalization of advanced pedagogical experience, and generalization of personal experience; independent education.

If the third situation related to the uniqueness of the past period of the development of the national school and pedagogy is considered, then a whole and complete structure will be formed before us.

I.P. Podlasiy defines the pedagogical function as "the direction of applying the professional knowledge and skills set for the pedagogue", as pedagogical work is related to teaching, education and upbringing of students, "the main task of the teacher states that "the task is to manage teaching, training, development and development processes". He sees the basis of pedagogical work in managing all the processes that take place in the formation of a person. The work done by the teacher can be called pedagogical management.

A.P. Voychenko said that the professional preparation of a graduate of a pedagogical university for pedagogical work is an integrated education, the components of which are interrelated, and the absence of at least one of them leads to an imbalance in the personality of a future teacher.

T.Z. Munavarova reveals this concept in the context of the relationship between theoretical and practical preparation of future teachers for pedagogical

activity. According to the level of professional-pedagogical training: high, medium and low, he divides the groups of students in the dissertation work.

Conclusions

Analysis of the theory and practice of training students of higher educational institutions of pedagogy for future professional activity leads to understanding of the special relevance and importance of the problem of forming the professional skills of future primary school teachers in a rapidly changing world.

The developed theoretical rules and experimental data allow us to draw the following conclusions:

1. Extensive analysis of literary sources, official materials and documents in various fields of modern science, as well as the analysis of studies devoted to solving the problem of preparing future teachers for professional pedagogical activities allowed us to come to this conclusion. The result of these works is the formation of their professional skills.

2. Based on the fact that perfection is the basis of activity, we have developed a structure of professional and pedagogical competencies, which includes motivational, material and procedural components with criteria and indicators. This, in turn, made it possible to develop a diagnostic technique to determine the level of formation of professional and practical skills of future primary school teachers in the process of teaching their mother tongue. The diagnostic results using questionnaires and tests showed that the preparation of students for their future professional activities in the educational process of the university is not effective enough, and for this it was determined that it is necessary to take sufficient measures to find ways to optimize it.

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